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	TESS-4C photometric bands	
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Abstract

This document shows the transmission of the filters used in TESS-4C, a four channel photometer used for measuring the night sky brightness. The dichroic filters have been characterized at Laboratorio de Investigación Científica Avanzada (LICA-UCM) of Universidad Complutense de Madrid to determine the spectral response. The final photometric bands for TESS-4C are also presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

TESS-4C (four channel TESS) is a photometer similar to TESS-W but with 4 channels. Each of them is fitted with the same optics and detector (TSL237). There is a threaded end to add color filters at the entrance of the channels to create different photometric bands by selecting the spectral range.

Several cheap filters have been tested to be used with TESS-4C and the final choice was RGB dichroic filters in combination with UVIR cut filters.

Figure 1. TESS-4C first version and a view of the inside filters.

Figure 2. TESS-4C second version with IR sensor added for cloud coverage estimate.

1.1. Setup

The standard procedure was used to determine the spectral response of the filters: the light from a lamp is injected to the monochromator after passing through the wheel of the sorting order filters. The monochromatic light is collimated in the optical train to illuminate the calibrated photodiode through a window of 5mm in diameter. The scanning at different consecutive wavelengths yields the reference spectrum. This result is compared with the spectrum measured when inserting the target filter into the optical path. To increase spectral resolution the LICA-UCM optical workbench was set to a wavelength step of 5nm. The spectral coverage covers from 350 to 1045 nm.

1.2. Measurements at LICA

In order to have the reference measurement (that without the filter in the path) we measured each filter and the reference (photodiode). The lamp was switched on at least 45 minutes before the test to assure brightness stabilization. The room temperature was 18-20°C degrees. Although the photodiode response should not change between different tests in consecutive days, we have measured its output for each filter set measure. The procedure described was performed without interruptions, except the time to change the filter in the optical path.

The spectral transmission tests were performed at LICA-UCM (2022/05/03) using the procedure described. The measurements included some routine tests to check that the workbench was working correctly. The transmission curves are obtained by comparing the reference signal at each wavelength with that obtained with the filter inserted in the path. The transmission curves were measured at the middle of each filter. The collimated beam is approximately of the diameter of the incoming window of the photodiode (5mm).

2. RESULTS

The spectral responses (transmission curves) of the dichroic RGB filters are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Transmission curves of the RGB dichroic filters.

A UVIR cut filter is needed to avoid the unwanted extra IR. The UVIR filter used is a UVIR650 with 50% drop at 650nm.

Figure 4. Same as Figure 3 with the UVIR5650 filter added.
The filter used in TESS-W (UVIR) is also shown.

Figure 5. The final response of the RGB filters after the UVIR650 is added to the optical path.

The green band is not broad enough and there is a spectral gap in the filter set. As a result the photometer is blind to some interesting wavelengths. This is why a different approach has been used to get RGB bands.

2.1.

3. RGB BANDS FOR TESS-4C

It is interesting to note that comparing the signal detected with the B and R bands obtained with the dichroic filter (plus the UVIR650) with the signal of a channel with only UVIR650 filter (clear channel) we can estimate the green signal.

Figure 6. The green synthetic filter is obtained by subtracting the signal of the R and B channels from that of the UVIR650 channel.

There is a channel with the same response as the TESS-W. The four channels are then:

channel	band	filters	comments
1	TESS-W	UVIR 750 nm	same as TESS-W
2	UVIR650	UVIR 650 nm	
3	B	UVIR 650 nm + dichroic B	Blue
4	R	UVIR 650 nm + dichroic R	Red

Figure 7. Same as Figure 6 with the TESS-W channel added.

TESS-W channel detects light in the region 650-750 nm. Comparing again TESS-W channel and the clear channel (UVIR650) another photometric band can be synthesized.

Figure 8. An extra synthetic band around 700nm as the results of comparing TESS-W channel and the clear (UVIR) channel signals.

4. COMPARISON WITH NIGHT SKY SPECTRA

We can compare the photometric bands' spectral responses with some night sky spectra.

Figure 9. Comparison of the bands and the sky spectrum at Madrid (2014) and at Calar Alto observatory.

5. EXPECTED RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT INPUT SPECTRA

The expected values obtained after observing a light source can be modelled using synthetic photometry. No absolute calibration is available and it is safe to use colors as ratios of the measures (frequency) in different channels.

Figure 10. Night sky spectra used for the synthetic photometry. 1st and 2nd refers to the first and the second part of the night respectively.

Figure 11. Lamps spectra used for the synthetic photometry.

Figure 12. Color-color diagram using the expected output for each channel.

Figure 13. Colors obtained in Tel Aviv 2022/08/06 by Noam Levin.